

FISH FARMING AND PREDATORS – AN ONGOING CONFLICT

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Abstract

In the established definition adopted by the FAO, aquaculture involves, in addition to private ownership of stocks, their protection from predators. Among the oldest conflicts between fish farmers and predators is that with fish-eating birds, the most formidable of which, in terms of damage caused and adaptability, are cormorants. This paper analyses the history of this conflict, the causes that have intensified and exacerbated it, the solutions proposed over time, and the recent approach that aims to maintain a balance between the need to conserve biodiversity and the objectives of economic and social sustainability in aquaculture.

1. Background

Given that environmental protection objectives, particularly those relating to the protection of habitats and species, have become a priority through the implementation of Directives 2009/147/EC and 92/43/EEC and the establishment of the European Natura 2000 ecological network at national level, fish farming has begun to be subject to constraints on the management of fish farms. In fact, the deterioration and loss of biodiversity is considered by some experts to be one of the most serious threats to the environment on a global scale, alongside climate change, with serious repercussions for the existence and development of human society. European Union policies on biodiversity conservation are based on the recognition of the value of environmental goods and services and aim to assess and incorporate them into new models of economic development.

The basis for these policies is the European ecological network Natura 2000, which is based on the premise that biodiversity conservation and sustainable socio-economic development are complementary, not antagonistic. Essentially, the impetus for the establishment of policies to protect bird species was the devastating impact that the following had on bird species: intensive agriculture, the widespread use of pesticides and chemical fertilisers, the destruction of wetlands through drainage and hydrotechnical works to regulate watercourses, and the hunting of species of hunting interest. For these reasons, the European Economic Community established, as early as 1979, the protection of all bird species living naturally in the wild, regardless of their status in relation to the degree of protection established by the International Union for Conservation of Nature.

In this context, although Article 2 of Directive 79/409/EEC, updated by Directive 2009/147/EC, states that: "Member States shall take the requisite measures to maintain the population of the species referred to in Article 1 (n.a. 'all species of birds living in the wild in the European territory of the Member States') at a level which meets

ecological, scientific and cultural requirements, while taking account of economic and recreational or requirements, in order to adapt the population of these species to that level", against the backdrop of the destruction of natural feeding and nesting areas in natural habitats, bird populations have grown uncontrollably without knowing the level that would meet the three conditions specified and without taking economic conditions into account. Reduced access to traditional feeding areas (natural habitats), the increase in the populations of certain species, especially fish-eating species, and the climate changes that have occurred in recent decades have meant that bird species that were previously non-existent or poorly represented in Romanian fish farms have become a real threat to the economic viability of fish farming. For example, the significant appearance of cormorants in inland Romania has been reported for about 20–25 years, and the significant appearance of pelicans in the Vaslui, Iași and Botoșani areas has been documented for about 15 years, with significant annual increases in numbers. In fact, university professor Ion Simionescu wrote about cormorants in 1923 [1]: "They rarely stray as far as the Vaslui region or the Răut Valley in Basarabia."

In fact, from a European historical perspective, attempts to regulate the relationship between fish farming and biodiversity are not new. The most important and current aspect of this trophically determined relationship is that related to fish-eating mammals and birds, which can thwart technological efforts. There is a long-standing debate at both European and, especially, national level about the measures that need to be taken to protect fish farms in ponds, ponds and reservoirs against the increasingly destructive attacks of certain species of birds or mammals that are under a more or less specific international protection regime, either because of their vulnerable conservation status or because they migrate. Conservationists accuse farmers of wanting to "barbarically" destroy bird species that have finally recovered their numbers and are resorting to measures taken to protect fish farming in the 1950s and 1960s. The species in question are cormorants (Phalacrocoracidae), pelicans (Pelecanidae), herons (Ardeidae) and, among mammals, otters (*Lutra lutra*). However, at least in Romania, dialogue between the parties involved, until recently inflamed by approximate approaches and unsupported opinions, has been replaced by a more balanced and objective approach. However, at least in Romania, the dialogue between the parties involved, which until recently was inflamed by approximate approaches and opinions without solid scientific support, continues to be at odds with the approaches of other EU Member States.

2. A brief history of the conflict and its causes

Looking back at the distant past of fish farming, we find the first mention of the cormorant in the first half of the 9th century, in German literature. Later, in the middle of the 13th century, the monk Albertus Magnus, canonised by the Catholic Church in 1931, described [2] the negative effects and especially the damage that cormorants caused to the carp ponds managed by monasteries. On 12 October 1377, the Holy Roman Emperor, Charles IV Wenceslaus, who had founded the first university in

Central Europe in Prague in 1348, ordered the inhabitants of Breslau/Wrocław "to kill and exterminate the 'water crows' wherever they live and nest [...] because they cause enormous damage to the fish in the water" [3]. Ancient literature is rich in such information, which is mentioned even in modern times. Almost all books on fish farming have a chapter on "the enemies of fish and the fight against them" [4], in which the species mentioned are invariably found. In fact, ornithologist Dionisie Linția described [5] his visit to Lake Șerbanu (Brăila County) between 16 and 17 May 1907: "Cormorants always breed in large colonies; these are all found near the Danube, except for the colony on Serpents' Island, which is the only one where the nests are located on cliffs. [...] In my estimation, this colony had between 1,700 and 2,000 occupied nests at that time. Most nests contained 3-4 or even 5 chicks, at various stages of development. [...] If we calculate only 3 chicks and two adult birds per nest, disregarding the number of immature individuals that also lived in this colony, the total number of cormorants can be estimated at a minimum of 10,000 specimens, and if we accept that each individual consumes an average of only 1 kg of fish per day, we can easily imagine how much fish the cormorants in the colony on Lake Șerbanu consumed daily. [...] The cormorant colony is dominated by a pungent and repulsive atmosphere; all the trees are covered with the liquid and sticky excrement of adult birds and the of chicks. Here you can find chicks that have fallen from their nests and drowned, as well as rotting fish on the surface of the water; and the infernal noise, with screams, shouts and cries, can be heard from a considerable distance and stuns you if you stay too long in such a gathering of vermin. [...] The greed of cormorants is enormous and can be explained by their rapid digestion; thus, they can catch 2-3 kg of fish daily, especially when they have to feed their ever-hungry chicks."

The major impact of cormorants and pelicans was felt in Europe after the measures taken in 1979, especially in Central and Eastern Europe, where traditional cyprinid farming in earthen fish ponds (ponds, lakes, reservoirs) is a millennial tradition. Although the population of two subspecies of great cormorant (the Atlantic cormorant - *Phalacrocorax carbo carbo* and the continental cormorant - *Phalacrocorax carbo sinensis*) has increased by three orders of magnitude, which is considered a success [6] by conservationists, fish farmers, commercial fishermen and recreational fishermen have denounced the devastating effect that this species has on the fishing industry, ranging from political lobbying and street demonstrations to the illegal destruction of their nests.

At international level, the case of cormorants has been discussed since 1994, at the meeting of the Scientific Committee of the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (Bonn Convention), when it was adopted by the Conference of the Parties at its fourth meeting (Nairobi, 7-11 June 1994). Recommendation 4.1 - Conservation and management of cormorants in the African-Eurasian region [7], which, among other things, recommended the development of a

plan for the management of cormorant populations, which, however, has not materialised in any concrete measures to date.

In the public sphere, both socio-political and scientific, data began to emerge on the magnitude of the damage caused by cormorants: "Cormorants feed exclusively on fish, with a daily food requirement of 400-600 g of fish. Cormorants are an 'opportunistic feeding' species, meaning they do not have a preference for certain fish species, but feed on any fish that can be caught most easily in the waters in question. They most commonly consume fish between 10 and 25 cm in length, but large specimens up to 60 cm and 1 kg in weight can also be caught by this bird.

To catch fish, cormorants dive vertically into the water, actively pursue their prey, catch it with their beaks and bring it to the surface. As birds that live in colonies, cormorants usually hunt in fairly large flocks that fly above the water. As a rule, each bird hunts alone, but often in groups of 25 to several hundred birds, which first surround the fish, resulting in a large percentage of the fish population being consumed in some waters in a relatively short period of time. As the cormorant, a large bird with a long lifespan, only begins to reproduce at around 3-5 years of age, the total population in Europe is probably (at least) 1.7-1.8 million birds.

Among other things, the Birds Directive (79/409/EC) adopted in 1979 and the measures it introduced to protect breeding sites have led to an excessive increase in the cormorant population, which has now spread far beyond its traditional breeding areas in regions where they had not previously been found. In many areas of the European Union, these large numbers have had an impact on local fish populations and fishing, making the presence of cormorants a problem throughout Europe.

To illustrate the problem for fish stocks in coastal and inland waters, it has been pointed out that, with a daily consumption of 400-600 g of fish, these birds are responsible for the disappearance of more than 300 000 tonnes of fish from European waters every year. In many Member States, the amount of fish consumed by cormorants is several times greater than the production obtained from professional fishing in inland waters and fish farms. For example, 300,000 tonnes is more than the combined aquaculture production of France, Spain, Italy, Germany, Hungary and the Czech Republic [8].

Important data on the negative impact of cormorants has been collected and analysed in projects funded by the European Commission under the Fifth Framework Programme for Research and Development, such as REDCAFE (2000–2005) and FRAP (completed in 2006). The REDCAFE project was continued through another project, INTERCAFE ("Interdisciplinary Initiative to Reduce pan-European Cormorant-Fisheries Conflicts"), funded through COST – European Cooperation in the field of Scientific and Technical Research between 2004 and 2008.

A study carried out for the European Parliament's Policy Department B mentions the existence of impact indicators such as: "the great cormorant consumes an average of

672 g of fish per day (between 441 and 1095 g/day); the size of the fish consumed ranges from 40 to 335 mm, with a preference for 100 to 149 mm, sizes at which density compensation mechanisms are totally ineffective" [9].

After 2011, another project funded by the European Commission through DG ENVI initiated the CorMan Platform, through which the Commission disseminates information about cormorants, cormorant populations, conflicts with the fishing sector and their management.

"Demonstrating unequivocal cause-and-effect relationships in environmental issues is not easy, and this is a particular challenge when analysing the interaction between cormorants and fish populations or stocks. This mainly reflects the inherent problems and uncertainties of obtaining reliable quantitative data on large bodies of water. For these reasons, it can be concluded that the absence of clear evidence means the absence of a problem. However, such arguments place an unreasonable burden on the fishing industry, and it must be recognised that the absence of clear, unequivocal evidence of losses does not mean that such losses are not occurring" [10].

If the problem of estimating losses in natural fish habitats is, as we have seen above, burdened by scientific controversy, mainly due to the lack of consistent, reliable and concrete information on fish stocks, in the case of fish farms where fish farming is based on the use of stocking formulas and very clear records of inputs and outputs, this becomes much simpler and involves fewer unknowns.

"As most members of the fishing industry do, carp farmers prefer to calculate the losses caused by cormorants as the difference between planned production and actual production. However, this method of calculation does not distinguish between the various causes of fish losses and therefore tends to overestimate the losses caused by cormorants. A more precise method of calculating losses caused by cormorants can be done by multiplying the number of cormorants observed on the farm by the number of feeding days and the average amount of food ingested per day" [11].

In this context, it should be noted that, in the present case, unlike the situations mentioned above, where research and data collection focused exclusively on cormorant populations, the range of fish-eating species faced by fish farmers, especially those practising traditional carps culture, is much more diverse, and among these, the following are much more numerous than cormorants: Bittern (*Botaurus stellaris*), Little Bittern (*Ixobrychus minutus*), Night Heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), Squacco Heron (*Ardeola ralloides*), Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*), Great Egret (*Egretta alba*), Purple Heron (*Ardea purpurea*), White-tailed Eagle (*Haliaeetus albicilla*), White-cheeked Tern (*Chlidonias hybridus*), Common Kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*), Otter (*Lutra lutra*) and Eurasian Coot – (*Fulica atra*), which, although not a fish eater, consumes feed and disturbs fish stocks in feeding areas.

Figure 1. Distribution and abundance of cormorants (source: <https://eurobirdportal.org/ebp/en/#home/PHACAR/r52weeks>)

3. Effects of the conflict and damage estimates

The assault of fish-eating birds and mammals, against which farmers are prevented from taking adequate measures to protect fish stocks due to specific restrictions in protected natural areas of Community interest, often interpreted rigidly by national authorities, has become an increasingly pressing problem in ensuring the economic viability of fish farming. The loss of the economic rationale for fish farming leads, and in some cases has already led, to the abandonment of fish farms, the abandonment of fish farming and the use of fish farming land for low-productivity agriculture, but with substantial payments for agri-environmental measures. The abandonment of fish farming has led to the disappearance of species specific to aquatic ecosystems and, consequently, to a loss of biodiversity in the region. "Fish farms are essential for the conservation of species characteristic of wetlands in Central and Eastern Europe" [12]. At the same time, it is confirmed at European level that: "It must be recognised, however, that compensation payments are not necessarily linked to financial losses, but rather to the fact that farmers need to be encouraged to maintain the heritage value of the landscape" [13].

On the other hand, the system of compensation for losses caused by fish-eating birds and mammals is practised in several Member States of the European Union, particularly those in Central and Eastern Europe, which practise cypriniculture using the same technological systems as Romania. It is worth mentioning that these compensations are granted even under the conditions of a derogation from the application of Directive 2009/147/EC, which is not the case in Romania.

Globally, aquaculture has become an alternative to fishing for natural resources to ensure the consumption of fish and aquatic organisms. According to the latest FAO report [14], fish production is predominantly (65%) carried out in traditional fish farms (ponds, fish ponds, reservoirs/lakes). The report also recognises the particularly important role that the technology used in such fish farms, namely the farming of several species to exploit all trophic niches, plays in improving water quality by extracting nutrients and increasing fish production.

With regard to the damage caused by populations of large cormorants, whether resident, migratory, nesting or wintering in various regions, there are two established methods for determining this damage [15], at least for fish farms, both of which are relatively accurate: the difference between planned production, in accordance with stocking levels and the amount of feed administered, excluding normal technological losses, according to the stage in the growth cycle, caused by various other factors, including normal losses caused by predators, and the method based on the period of presence of fish-eating birds, their expected daily fish consumption rate (from the literature) and the average market price of the fish species stocked in the respective fish farm.

However, in the public dialogue on this topic, it is regularly argued that there are no published data or scientific papers from farmers that could constitute a reference database for estimating the accuracy of these calculation methods in specific situations.

According to these calculation methods, the losses recorded by cyprinid farms as a result of the intensification of the conflict between cormorants and fish stocks, determined between 2004 and 2007, were within the following limits: Germany 90.9–145.5 EUR/ha/year, Czech Republic 49.1–96.3 EUR/ha/year, Poland 14.5–30.3 EUR/ha/year, Israel 92.1–144.7 EUR/ha/year, Hungary 41–47.3 EUR/ha/year. It should be noted, however, that in the German state of Brandenburg, for example, compensation ranging from EUR 18 to EUR 699/ha was granted depending on the season and age class if the losses caused by protected species exceeded normal technological figures [16].

In Romania, based on data [17] monitored in seven cyprinid farms, which include all types of aquaculture infrastructure, from ponds, fishponds and lakes to reservoirs with and without feeding, over six consecutive years, it was found that the annual loss caused by fish predators

(mainly cormorants) amounts to 134 kg of fish/ha. At a weighted average value of EUR 2.38/kg, this results in an average annual loss of EUR 318.92/ha.

On the other hand, according to data communicated by Romania to the European Commission between 2013 and 2018, based on estimates by the Romanian Ornithological Society, the situation was as follows (the arithmetic mean between the minimum and maximum values presented in the communication was considered):

Species	Passage (individuals)	Wintering (individuals)	Nesting (individuals)	Comment	Annual TOTAL
Great cormorant	35 000 [18]	20 000	32 000	An additional 28,640 specimens surviving beyond 8 weeks, resulting from the reproduction of the 16,000 pairs) [19]	95 640
Pygmy cormorant	14 000	12 500	20 000	Another 32,000 specimens that survive for at least 3 weeks after reproduction [20]	66 000
Common Pelican	30 000	0	13 000 [21]	8,500 surviving chicks	51 500

Specimens that have not reached sexual maturity (those aged up to 4 years) were not taken into account.

Species	No. of specimens per year	No. of days present/individual	Daily consumption, kg/day/individual	Total days presence per year	Consumption kg per year	Average price, EUR/kg	Annual consumption value, EUR
Great cormorant	95.640	210	0,768	20.084.400	15.424.819	2,38	36.711.069
Pygmy cormorant	66.000	210	0,3715	13.860.000	5.148.990	2,38	12.254.596
Pelicans	53.420	180	1.2	9.615.600	11.538.720	2,38	27.462.153
TOTAL	215.060				32.112.529		76.427.819

The area used for aquaculture in Romania is 100,000 ha and, in conclusion, the loss of income is EUR 764.28 per hectare, solely due to these species.

It can be assumed that only one third of the damage occurs on farms, and therefore the annual loss in fish farms can be estimated, based on this calculation, at EUR 254.76/ha/year, caused solely by these three species. In principle, up to 24 species of fish-eating birds and mammals can be found in a fish farm, consuming exclusively, preferentially or accidentally fish of different sizes/ages.

In this context, an important element in describing the impact on fish stocks is the number of injured specimens that could not be consumed and the effect on the maintenance of fish stocks due to the way in which cormorants, in particular, hunt their

prey. The stress caused by attacks from cormorants or pelicans leads to weight loss, inefficient feed consumption and, ultimately, a reduction in the farmer's projected financial return. On the other hand, injured specimens are unmarketable and are sources of pathogen spread in fish farms.

4. Methods of reducing losses

In analysing the methods that can be used in aquaculture to reduce losses caused by fish-eating species under a certain protection regime, it is necessary to start from the text of the Birds Directive, which has been transposed verbatim into national legislation. Although, according to the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, competence regarding the form and means of achieving the objectives of the Directive is assigned to national authorities, Article 5 of the Directive imposes the following restrictions:

" (a) the deliberate killing or capture of the species concerned, by whatever means;
(b) deliberate destruction of, or damage to, nests or eggs or removal of nests;
(c) the taking of eggs in the wild and their retention, even if empty;
(d) deliberately disturbing these birds, particularly during the breeding or rearing season, if such disturbance is relevant in the context of the objectives of this Directive;
(e) keeping in captivity birds of species whose hunting and capture is prohibited."

On the other hand, Article 9 of the same Directive specifies that Member States may apply derogations from the provisions of Article 5 where there is no other satisfactory solution to prevent considerable damage to crops, livestock, forests, fisheries and water. We will skip over the vague legal wording of the above-mentioned articles (e.g. how to determine the relevance of a disturbance, or the degree of satisfaction of a derogation measure, or the concrete meaning of considerable damage), which has been taken over as such in Romanian legislation without providing the necessary clarifications, although the necessary conditions existed from a legal point of view, and we present a summary of the methods used and analysed to date.

Over the last 25 years, a series of studies, mainly funded by European Union institutions, have been carried out to determine how to achieve community management of the rapidly expanding great cormorant population, which is in increasing conflict with economic, environmental and social objectives.

Thus, including within the REDCAFE project [22], the efficiency, acceptability, practicability and costs of various options tried by farmers in European countries, including in Israel, were analysed to determine how satisfactory the existing solutions on the market are. Below is a summary of the methods used, all of which should have been part of the derogation system.

These methods can be classified into three categories: resource management, exclusion methods, and extraction methods.

The first category includes habitat management and fish stock management. Habitat management involves modifying habitats in such a way as to increase the reproductive success rate of fish fauna in order to cope with predators. The method is only applicable in natural habitats and is considered effective over periods of months to years. In

aquaculture, habitat management involves increasing turbidity, but cyprinid farms operate in conditions of high turbidity, which leads to the conclusion that the method is ineffective.

Various solutions have been tested for fish stock management, such as: changing the stocking period (ineffective), changing the stocking frequency (ineffective), changing the stocking density, either by increasing (ineffective) or decreasing (ineffective) it, changing the size of the fish stocked (ineffective given the diversity of sizes that some fish-eating predators can consume). On the other hand, switching to stocking larger fish is much more expensive.

Also included in the category of methods relating to the management of fish stocks in fish farms is the location of the most sensitive fish species and sizes near the centre of human activity or near buildings. However, cormorants were not deterred from searching for food unless active measures were also used (e.g. noise sources, gunshots, human patrols, etc.).

Exclusion methods involve either installing bird barriers, physical enclosures with narrow mesh systems (mesh sizes mostly < 20 cm) using wire, rope or string in the form of a grid. Narrow mesh systems (10-20 cm spacing) have been widely used in salmonid farming units in Europe, mainly using polyester twine. Sometimes these systems have also been used in other types of aquaculture facilities, such as small ponds in cyprinid farms (pre-development ponds, wintering ponds, etc.). These systems have a high visual impact, as the ropes and wires are mounted 4-5 m above head height on wooden poles to avoid negative impact on the daily operations of the protected fish farms. The effectiveness of these systems is low for medium-sized or small bird species (cormorants) and relatively low for large species (grey heron, pelican, spoonbill). The systems require maintenance after severe weather, especially ice storms and storms. Problems with this technique have involved the possibility of non-targeted water bird species colliding with wires and ropes when attempting to land on protected ponds, especially at night. Cormorants can quickly learn how to avoid wires and ropes.

Partial closures with narrow mesh have also been used on approximately 10% of the water surface to provide refuge for fish when attacked by cormorants. Fish stocks receive additional feed in the protected part of the pond. At night, carp can then use the entire pond for feeding. The effectiveness of this method is questionable given the underwater behaviour of cormorants. A variation of this method is the installation of vertical, parallel nets (placed 5-10 m apart) in the form of submersible fences that prevent cormorants from diving. The effectiveness of this method is considered modest, especially in the context of the technological operations that are carried out periodically in fish ponds during the growing season and the high costs involved.

Finally, methods involving wildlife management include non-lethal techniques, lethal techniques, and a combination of both. The latter appear to be the most effective according to data obtained in Israel (Hula Valley). Non-lethal techniques primarily involve human harassment (patrols on foot, in vehicles or by boat) with only short-term effectiveness (hours or sometimes days). In order to keep cormorants away for longer

periods of time, an almost constant human presence was considered necessary. Therefore, the costs can be high if working time has to be paid for (e.g. salaries). Another series of methods consists of sound deterrent techniques sirens (ineffective or effective for a few hours at best), ineffective horns), gas cannons (effective only in the short term, for a few hours). Sounds (including ultrasound) can negatively affect other non-target species, as well as workers and other people.

Pyrotechnics/fireworks or just visual elements (lasers) can also be used as part of sound and visual methods. However, their use has been restricted since due to legal restrictions, especially since noise or lasers can have negative impacts on other wild animals and humans.

Live ammunition ("shoot-to-scare") can also be used in the series of non-lethal sound methods. It has been more widespread than the use of pyrotechnics, as live ammunition is often cheaper and easier to find. There are also fewer legal restrictions on its use. Again, despite its widespread use, it has generally been considered effective only in the short term (for hours or up to days).

Visual deterrent techniques involve the use of static effigies, simple human figures or scarecrows, animated effigies, moving and/or in combination with automatic sound devices, such as Mylar strips, CDs, etc., which are reflective. They are most effective when used in conjunction with sound sources and if they are moved regularly. Their effectiveness lasts only a few days until predators become accustomed to them. On the other hand, they are a source of both visual and water pollution.

The combination of audio and visual techniques is effective for a few days.

Lethal techniques, which are most contested by environmental organisations, involve shooting adults and immature specimens to reinforce non-lethal harassment or to reduce the number of birds in certain places or regions.

Shooting can only be effective for weeks or months, especially when there are stable bird populations and a low bird replacement rate. The combination of using shooting to scare and shooting to kill has proven to be the most effective technique for cormorants. The effectiveness of this method can also be increased by adopting a pan-European management plan for the great cormorant population, an initiative described below.

5. Reconciliation solutions

Given that, in 1994, the great cormorant population was found to have exceeded the optimal population level, the species was removed from the annexes to the Convention. In 1996, the European Parliament adopted a resolution [23] calling for urgent measures to "restore the natural balance" seriously affected by the very large populations of great cormorants that had appeared in areas of Europe where they had not existed or had been poorly or moderately represented, and as a result, the species was removed in 1997 and from the annexes to the Birds Directive, but remaining protected as a migratory species.

The devastating effects on fish farming and even fishing have been amplified by the procedures, and associated costs, of applying Article 9 of the Birds Directive regarding the approval of derogations for species that cause damage to fish farming.

Consequently, in 2008, the European Parliament adopted the Kindermann Report [24], which called on the European Commission, among other things, to: 'invite the Commission to examine all legal means available to reduce the negative effects of cormorant populations on fisheries and aquaculture, and, when drawing up an initiative to promote aquaculture in Europe, to take into account the positive effects of a European population management plan and, in this context, to present proposals for solutions to the cormorant problem" on the basis that: "the risk of considerable damage increases disproportionately as the number of cormorants in a region approaches the absorption capacity of large bodies of water, which at the same time leads to a significant decrease in the effectiveness of countermeasures taken at local level'.

In a position paper published in 2004 by the leading bird conservation organization [25], the authors acknowledge that there are no studies on the number of cormorants existing before 1950, when their population declined significantly, but that by 1970 it had made a remarkable recovery.

The issue of cormorants and other birds that feed exclusively on fish (pelicans, herons, bitterns, spoonbills and 30 other species) has been and remains a controversial topic, but there are some indisputable facts and figures:

1. The population of great cormorants in Romania has far exceeded the abstract values set out in Article 2 of Directive 2009/147/EC;
2. Birds that feed exclusively on fish cause considerable damage to fisheries and waters;
3. Scientific data on the daily food consumption of several species of fish-eating birds show the following figures:
 - a. Pygmy cormorant (*Ph. pygmeus*) – 371.5 g/day [26];
 - b. Great cormorant (*Ph. carbo*) – 768 g/day [27];
 - c. Dalmatian pelican (*Pelecanus oncorhynchus*) – 1200 g/day.

Although various European Parliament resolutions called for a reconsideration of protection measures, no concrete action has yet been taken to establish the size of the cormorant population in line with the objective set out in Article 2 of the Birds Directive. In addition to these EU legislative documents and projects funded by the European Commission, organisations representing aquaculture farmers, particularly fish farmers in Central and Eastern Europe, have exerted constant pressure through position papers, resolutions or recommendations such as those issued by participants in a series of international conferences of carp farmers (Poland in 2011 and 2013, the Czech Republic in 2015, Croatia in 2017, Germany in 2019 and Hungary in 2022 [28]), by the European Federation of Aquaculture Producers [29] or by the Aquaculture Advisory Council [30].

Ultimately, all these related actions appear to be materialising in a European Cormorant Population Management Plan, which is in its final stages of development and is due to be launched in early June by the Polish Presidency of the Council of the European

Union. The document was drafted by the European Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture Advisory Commission (EIFAAC) – a body of the FAO.

The European management plan for the great cormorant proposed by EIFAAC [31] following extensive consultation with all stakeholders is tailored and involves a series of steps:

- 1.assessment of the fish-cormorant interaction system, related economic aspects and the underlying policy objectives and targets;
- 2.formulating management measures;
- 3.choosing a course of action;
- 4.implementation of management actions, monitoring of changes in cormorant, fish, aquaculture and ecosystem characteristics, regional cooperation and compensation for damage to fisheries and aquaculture;
- 5.evaluating and adjusting the plan's objectives and targets in the future.

Structural measures will relate, among other things, to:

- Introducing standardised rapid applications and approvals for lethal control in accordance with Article 9;
- Proposing to change the protection status of the great cormorant under the Bern Convention from a species not listed in Annex III to a species listed as an exception;
- Establishing spatial management to reduce the impact of cormorant predation on fish by designating 'cormorant-free zones' for fish and 'unregulated zones' for cormorants. As such, it will be necessary to develop zonal management plans in which lethal control is linked to documented impact, particularly in areas of high conflict;
- Systematic lethal control to reduce the European cormorant population to a manageable level and to protect fish populations to achieve a favourable conservation status and water bodies to achieve good ecological status or potential;
- Establishment of a target population of breeding pairs of cormorants in the European distribution range of 150,000 breeding pairs (the number existing in 1994, when the recovery of the great cormorant population was recognised), pursuant to Article 2 of the Birds Directive;
- The procedure for establishing compensation payments, including damage reporting, payment criteria and damage payment, must be standardised in all European countries.

Some of the concrete measures provided for in this plan, which is expected to be implemented by the European Commission from 2026, relate to the funding that will be allocated for:

- The development, promotion and implementation of conflict prevention and mitigation measures, including non-lethal deterrent measures, predation thresholds and the resilience of fish stocks or populations;
- Establishing and operationalising damage/loss reporting systems, damage assessment systems and compensation for affected fisheries and aquaculture entrepreneurs;

- Establishment and operation of joint initiatives for data collection and monitoring, reporting and dissemination;
- Establishing and maintaining a secretariat that will provide a platform for cormorant management, including a data centre, coordination of actions between countries, support for awareness raising and capacity building, and reporting to the EC and EIFAAC.

6. Interim conclusions

What is important to note at this stage may also be a summary of the evolution of the predator-fish farming conflict:

- ▶ For the first time, one of the confusing provisions of the Birds Directive, namely that in Article 2, concerning the level of cormorant populations that meet ecological, scientific and cultural conditions, while also taking into account economic and recreational conditions, in order to adapt the population of this species to that level, is being implemented.
- ▶ According to Article 288 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, the Directive is binding on each Member State to which it is addressed as to the result to be achieved, leaving the national authorities the choice of form and methods, and one of the results is the adaptation of the population, in this case the great cormorant, to the level mentioned. The opposition of some Member States, including Romania, to the means and methods established by the Directive can only be interpreted as a violation of its provisions, since the mandatory result, namely maintaining the population at a level that complies with biodiversity conservation criteria in accordance with economic criteria, is not achieved;
- ▶ Traditional fish farming facilities are a net provider of environmental services to society, covering all four ecosystem functions supply (providing high-quality food, fibre, resources for medicinal products, sources of fertiliser for agriculture, water for irrigation), regulation (local microclimate, regulation of groundwater and surface water, extraction and storage of phosphorus, nitrogen and carbon nutrients), cultural (part of the cultural heritage of human society, providing sources of inspiration, areas for relaxation and support (determining role in nutrient recycling, preserving wetlands, forming fertile soils, preserving biodiversity by providing shelter, feeding, breeding and nesting sites for hundreds of bird species));
- ▶ The abandonment of fish farming activities in land basins, which has been happening for the last ten years, due to the decrease in economic performance caused by the lack of a legal framework for coherent management of predators in fish farms, affects not only the environmental services mentioned above, but above all it is a threat to biodiversity of which the great cormorant is a marginal part.

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